

DIGITALIZATION IN THE PRODUCTION OF LAND CADASTRE INFORMATION AND CREATION OF THE CONTENT OF LEGISLATIVE DOCUMENTS ON GEO-INFORMATION

Asadova Manzura Axatovna¹, Axtamov Suxrobjon², Muxamadov Qamoriddin³, Bobojonov Saidjon⁴

¹ Master of Bukhara branch of the Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization Engineers, ² Master of Bukhara branch of the Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization Engineers, ³ Student of the Bukhara branch of the Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization Engineers, ⁴ Student of the Bukhara branch of the Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization Engineers

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5083940>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 01st July 2021

Accepted: 05th July 2021

Online: 07th July 2021

KEY WORDS

use of digital technologies, digitization, information and communication technologies.

ABSTRACT

In the article, digitization processes play an important role in the field of land cadastre, as well as development processes in all areas today. In particular, in the production of land cadastral information is the digitization and coverage of the essence of the legislation on geoinformation.

Introduction

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PF-5953-con dated March 2, 2020 on the State Program for the implementation of the Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021 in the "Year of Science, Enlightenment and Digital Economy" Explained the content of the Decree No. PF-6079 of October 5 "On approval of the Strategy" Digital Uzbekistan-2030 "and measures for its effective implementation." In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 5, 2020 "On approval of the Strategy" Digital Uzbekistan-2030 "and measures for its effective implementation" PF-6079, the

following measures are taken to improve digital skills in public administration:

development and continuous improvement of the mechanism for improving the skills and competencies of civil servants in the field of information and communication technologies;

holding events (forums, seminars, conferences, etc.) to discuss new achievements in promising areas of digitalization in the real sector of the economy;

training, support and promotion of talented IT specialists and creating opportunities for their development to prevent the outflow of talented people from the country;

Problem statement: development of mechanisms for assessing the skills of using digital technologies, taking into account the following aspects: information literacy (the ability to find the information needed for decision-making); computer literacy (ability to work with digital devices); media literacy (opportunity to critically study the media); communicative literacy (ability to use modern digital means of communication); formation of a positive attitude to technological innovations (new technologies);

formation and implementation of requirements to the basic powers of the digital economy for each level of education in the education system, (taking into account the model of powers) to ensure their continuity;

creation of a single electronic platform for distance learning using modern educational technologies and new mechanisms for assessing the qualifications of employees to improve the skills of government officials;

engaging employees responsible for the introduction and development of the digital economy, modern information technologies and communications without complying with the main positions of employees and the occupational classification of employees in terms of minimum level of education and professional qualifications.]

Analysis and results: The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On State Cadastres", the Regulation on the procedure for creating and maintaining the Unified System of State Cadastres (UNCS), approved by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 16, 2005 No. 66, other normative legal acts

documents and in accordance with this Regulation.

The following are the basic principles of the AODC:

Coverage of all communication facilities in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

☒ application of a single system of spatial coordinates and a single topographic basis;

☒ uniformity of the methodology of formation of cadastral information on all objects;

☒ reliability, visibility and documentation of cadastral information;

☒ Transparency of cadastral information.

☒ coordinates the work of cadastral services (authorized persons);

☒ Controls the quality of incoming information, is responsible for their reliability and inclusion of communication objects in the geoinformation system;

☒ Provides a map of the location of communication facilities in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

☒ determines the procedure and conditions of use of cadastral information by interested legal entities and individuals;

☒ Provides prompt provision of cadastral information to the State Registration Service;

☒ annually, in the prescribed manner, submits to the State Committee "Geodesy and Cadastre" a report on the status and use of communication facilities for inclusion in the database of the State Agency for Geodesy and Cadastre.

Conclusion. On the basis of the State Committee for Land Resources, Geodesy, Cartography and State Cadastre of

the Republic of Uzbekistan under the State Tax Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 7, 2020 No PF-6061 "On

measures to radically improve the system of land accounting and state cadastre" The Cadastre Agency (hereinafter - the Cadastre Agency) was established.

References:

1. <http://www.iiasa.ac.at> – Modeling Land-Use and Land-Cover Changes
2. <mailto:apex@apex-realty.ru>
3. <mailto:site@tikhvin.org>